

THE STATE OF HISTORICAL AND ARCHITECTURAL STRUCTURES IN THE KASKAKADARYA AND SURKHANDARYA REGIONS IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778032>

Annotation. This article discusses attention to ancient cultural heritage sites on the territory of Southern Uzbekistan during the years of independence, their repair and restoration, the significance of our architectural masterpieces in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, and also discusses the topic and analyzes it using the example of historical and architectural monuments of the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions.

Keywords: The cities of Karshi and Shakhrisabz, the city of Termiz, Amir Temur and the Timurids, significance, cultural heritage, historical monuments, repair and restoration, architectural structure, fortification, archeology.

The formation of a national ideology in the field of spirituality in recent years, the first place in the issue of educating the younger generation in the spirit of our cultural heritage, respect for our rich traditions and universal values, loyalty to the ideas of our great country and independence indicates the correctness of the policy carried out in Uzbekistan[1.1].

Recent trends in the global economy, such as the rapid development of tourism and recreation, have a significant impact on the Central Asian region, including Uzbekistan, in various regions and countries[2.1]. The visit to the places of pilgrimage is connected with the tourism sector, which in the 21st century became the most advantageous sphere in the world. Now he is in third place after the field of automotive and oil refining. The development of the tourism sector is important in strengthening the national and regional economy[3.1].

After our country gained independence, there were wide opportunities to study the history of our homeland and express unbiased opinions about it. At the same time, wide avenues were opened for the repair and restoration of thousands of historical and architectural monuments and old buildings on the territory of our Motherland. On the issue of self-awareness, restoration of true history and creation of the history of a renewed Uzbekistan, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed the following opinion: "Building a new

Uzbekistan means studying our recent and distant history, our unique and rare cultural treasures in more depth and, relying on them, continuing our path of independent national development at a new stage” [4.31].

Two ancient territories of southern Uzbekistan - Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions - are also home to many historical and architectural monuments. Currently, a total of more than two thousand objects of tangible cultural heritage in these two regions are included in the state register, and about a thousand historical objects are assigned public inspectors [5]. This data shows the scale of work being carried out to preserve the cultural and historical heritage of our country and pass it on to future generations.

The city of Karshi is one of the ancient cities of our country with a history of almost three thousand years. Today, this ancient settlement preserves more than 60 masterpieces of the past, of which 28 are archaeological sites, 6 are monumental monuments, 1 is a place of interest, and 25 are historical and architectural structures [6].

Historical sources indicate that by the 20th century, there were more than 100 mosques and about 50 madrasahs in the city of Karshi [7]. Unfortunately, most of these ancient monuments have not survived to this day. Only four madrasahs have survived near the area of the city, which is called the “old city” by local residents: Khoja Abdulazizboy, Bekmir Kazakh, Sharofboy (this madrasah is now almost in a state of disrepair), and Kilichboy.

Repair, restoration and strengthening of some historical monuments located in the territory of this ancient city were carried out in connection with the celebrations of the 2700th anniversary of the city of Karshi. In particular, based on the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 452 dated September 29, 2004 and the resolution of the khokim of Kashkadarya region No. X-417/10 dated October 15, 2004 “On preparation and holding of the 2700th anniversary of the city of Karshi”, repair, restoration and improvement works were carried out in the Odina mosque on Registan Square, the Old Sardoba, Khoja Abdulazizboy and Bekmir Kazakh (Bekmurodboy) madrasahs of the city [8.5-6].

One of the important historical and architectural monuments located in the territory of the city of Karshi is the Kokgumbaz mosque, which, according to sources, was built by the Khan of Bukhara, Abdullakhan II, in 999 AH (1590–1591) [9, 498]. Due to the widespread use of blue and light-colored tiles on the dome of the building, this prayer place was called the “Kokgumbaz mosque” by the local population. Unfortunately, the dome and adjacent parts of the structure

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were significantly damaged as a result of an earthquake at the end of the 19th century.

In the 20th century, this historical monument was renovated and strengthened several times. In particular, partial renovations were carried out in 1957, 1971, and 1975, and in 1982, the monument underwent extensive renovations [10, 147]. In 1996, on the occasion of the 660th anniversary of the birth of Amir Temur, master architects from Samarkand also renovated this building [11].

On the occasion of the 2700th anniversary of the city of Karshi, extensive repair, restoration, and strengthening work was carried out on a number of ancient monuments, including the mosques of Odina, Nav, Khanaqoh, Qum village, Chorgumbaz in the Kosan district, the mausoleum of Abu Ubayda ibn al-Jarrah, the holy shrines of Mubarak al-Marvazi in the Mubarak district, and Hazrati Imam in the city of Shahrisabz [12].

With its 2,700-year history, the city of Shahrisabz and its surrounding areas have a number of ancient monuments, some of which have survived to this day. Currently, there are more than 220 cultural heritage sites in this area, more than 50 of which are registered as historical and architectural structures [13]. One of the oldest monuments in Shahrisabz, also known as the Green City, is the White Palace, built in the 14th–15th centuries. This monument has been preserved through various renovations and restorations.

A program for the restoration of historical and architectural monuments associated with the names of Amir Temur and Mirzo Ulugbek was developed in the city of Shahrisabz on January 5, 1993. Within the framework of this program, the hydrogeological conditions of the remains of the Jahongir Mausoleum were also studied and appropriate measures were taken to ensure its protection [14, 71].

On the occasion of the anniversary of Mirzo Ulugbek, a special expedition was organized in 1993 to study ancient monuments, and a total of 106.4 million soums were allocated for the renovation of the Shamsiddin Kulol Mausoleum, the Kokgumbaz Mosque, the Dorut-tilovat Complex, and the Gumbazi Sayyidon Mausoleum [15].

Also, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 630 dated December 29, 1994 “On the Celebration of the 660th Anniversary of the Birth of Amir Temur”, in 1995 the arch of the White Palace building was repaired by the Shahrisabz enterprise “Scientific

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Repair of Historical Monuments”. In this process, conservation work was also carried out on some parts of the structure [16].

One of the historical and architectural structures renovated in connection with the 660th anniversary of the birth of Amir Temur is the Chubin Madrasah. This madrasah is part of a complex of monuments dating back to the 16th–19th centuries, and the ancient structure has been renovated several times to this day [17, 146]. In-depth scientific research, restoration and reconstruction of this historical object began in 1990–1991. As part of these processes, archaeological research was carried out, as a result of which it was determined that the main and original part of the madrasah complex was built at the end of the 15th century.

Partial repair and renovation works were carried out at the Chubin Madrasah in 1992–1995. In 1994, large-scale restoration works were carried out on the gatehouse of the historical monument and adjacent buildings. In 1995, the Uzbek Restoration Institute developed a project for the renovation of the Chubin Madrasah, and based on this project, the madrasah was completely restored [18, 1–2].

Also, in accordance with the Resolution No. 102 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2002 “On preparations for the celebration of the 2700th anniversary of the city of Shakhrisabz”, the improvement of the territories of a number of historical monuments in the city and related repairs were determined. In accordance with this resolution, extensive work was carried out to preserve historical objects and give them an aesthetic appearance.

Based on this resolution, restoration and reconstruction works of the Chubin Madrasah, as well as landscaping and greening of the surroundings of the ancient monument were carried out. 80 million soums were allocated for these works [19]. Also, according to the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a total of 1.3 billion soums were allocated for the repair and restoration of historical and architectural monuments located in the city of Shakhrisabz, and for the improvement of the territories of unique complexes.

The Surkhan oasis also houses a number of mausoleums of sheikhs, saints, and pirs. One of the most famous of them is the Sultan Saodat - Sayyids' Complex. This architectural complex was formed over about seven centuries and was built in the 10th-17th centuries, as recorded in historical sources [20, 110].

This sacred place, where the Sayyids settled forever, contains about twenty mausoleums, containing the graves of about 170 Sayyids.

The complex of Sultan Saodat mausoleums, which has survived to this day, is located around a 70-meter courtyard, which was formed as a result of architectural and construction work in different periods. Several archaeological studies have been carried out on the territory of this historical monument. In particular, in the November 11, 2017 issue of the newspaper "Surkhon Tongi" by the head of the department of the Termez Archaeological Museum, Sh. Rajabov, in the article "A tombstone worthy of centuries" information about the excavations carried out in this complex is provided. According to this article, during the research conducted at the end of the 20th century, a tombstone (91.5 x 61 x 9 cm in size) dating back to the 11th-12th centuries was found. Unfortunately, this tombstone has not been fully preserved archaeologically [21, 4].

In conclusion, we can say that one of the most important tasks of our time is to strengthen, repair, restore and restore historical and architectural monuments built over centuries in the territories of our country and pass them on to future generations. It is also no exaggeration to say that the role of ancient structures in educating our younger generation in the spirit of creativity and innovation is of incomparable importance.

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